

Is female education 'gendered' and procedurally yet substantively practiced' in China? Insights from a systematic review and the practical theory

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Abstract

Female education in China is an over-researched area, yet it does not provide enough evidence on the country's exact pattern of female education practice. On the one hand, the National Plan of 2010–2020 emphasises equal education policies regardless of gender type. On the other hand, reported research raises several gendered and procedural yet substantive practices of female education in China. Thus, it was essential to conduct this study to inform policymakers, practitioners and researchers on the status of this area, based on a systematic review of 47 eligible included studies conducted between 2009 and 2020, including quantitative, qualitative, and mixed designs. The review answers two questions: (1) What are the substantive findings of qualitative synthesis on gender equity of female education in China? (2) Regardless of the existence or absence of gender inequity, what patterns of female education exist, and what kind of framework or model could be proposed to reform female education in China? The PRISMA guideline and SPIDER tool were used to conduct and report this study. The practical theory was also used—proposing a model that may

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serve to diagnose as well as intervene in the conflict of female education equity in China. Findings and conclusions showed that both gender equity and gender inequity are disadvantageous at short-term and long-term levels. For this reason, *relativism* might help to reduce the impact of these two patterns. While cultural and social capital is still the main impacting factor on gender equity in any country, reform should take place. *Relativism* could be achieved through reasonable understanding and interpretation of the sources that form the cultural and social capital. It takes place also by preventing the causes of gender gaps. These include over-interpretation and under-interpretation of gender roles, mainly those which are female. Gender should never be used as a factor in human capital.

KEYWORDS

education equity, female education development, female education equity, practical theory, systematic review

Context and implications

Rationale for this study

To examine the claim of female education in China being gendered and procedurally yet substantively practised or not; we therefore did a systematic review of the quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method design studies on female education equity in China between 2009 and 2020.

Why the new findings matter

It is not clear whether China's female education system manifests gender or another type of inequality, or what patterns characterise it compared to other countries. This systematic review introduces a framework to understand the female education system in China through the different patterns which govern human capital, social capital, economic capital and cultural capital.

Implications for education researchers and policymakers

This study has implications for policymakers, decision-makers, teachers and researchers interested in conducting systematic reviews in education science.

- The literature review identified some themes: gender equity and minorities, gender equity in higher and vocational education, national development and policy adjustment, Chinese context-based social factors, misconceptualisation of gender equity, quantitative inequity, and finally, mission schools;
- The systematic review identified themes like minority discrimination, discrimination between rural and urban areas, the impact of education on health and psychology,

educational leadership and policy, educational attainment/performance, and social capital;

- Using the five constituents of the Practical Theory led to the proposal of a model presenting patterns of female education, helping to reform female education; and
- Policymakers, practitioners and researchers on female education might find it informative and practical to conduct more systematic reviews on female education when applying this theory and other related theories.

INTRODUCTION

Gender inequity is an international phenomenon that exists everywhere with variations in pattern from one country to another. These relative similarities and differences are impacted by several factors of culture, religion, economy and many other factors. To understand the gender education system in China—the context of this study—this part is divided into several sections. First, an overview of gender equity in the world is introduced. Second, gender equity in China is synthesised. The rest of the paper presents the rationale, the objectives, the methods, results, discussion and appendix.

GENDER EQUITY WORLDWIDE

Gender theory was initially studied in the West based on biological differences between the two sexes—extending later to different dimensions, including education, according to MacDonald (as cited in Alemán & Renn, 2002, p. 76). Western countries have noticeably taken the lead in terms of gender equality. For instance, Nidiffer states, ‘today women of all ages and backgrounds are part of every aspect of higher education’. They are however also over-represented in such sectors (as cited in Alemán & Renn, 2002, p. 3), even though, as Tidball argues, ‘women in academe still live and work in a male-dominated world and institutional environment, where access may have indeed improved, but the quality of that access remains a critical issue’ (as cited in Alemán & Renn, 2002, p. xv). Gender equity is described as a global issue that the EU itself has been trying hard to improve, with a primary focus on higher education. Rees stated: ‘the European Union and all its member states provide equal treatment for all regardless of sex, race, and ethnic origin, sexual orientation, age, disability, and religious and political beliefs and that gender equality be mainstreamed in all EU policies’, which has been the policy since 1996 (as cited in Sagaria, 2007, p. 7). The vast amount of literature and research on gender equality, female gender equality, and equality in having a say has resulted in movements calling for male gender equality. Weaver-Hightower clearly stated that ‘from Australia to England, from the United States to Canada, and from Iceland to Germany, a noticeable panic has developed and grown around boys’ education’ (as cited in Bank et al., 2007, p. 717). Concerning female education in Canada, David ascertains that ‘gender equity could become a central part of educational effectiveness for both parents and children of this and future generations who are increasingly expected to forge their own gender, sexual and work identities’ (as cited in Ali et al., 2004, p. 26).

Regardless of the very early views attributed to Aristotle and Plato—in which it is both a blessing and a curse that a woman is not equal to a man or remarkably different regarding maturation and menarche—there has been significant progress on bridging gender gaps (Hufnagel, 2012, p. 15). Hence, according to Kite (as cited in Worell, 2002, p. 561) there will

always be ‘gender role violators,’ who in one way or another ‘do not conform to expected gender roles,’ that is, ‘shared expectations that define how women and men should behave (prescriptive) and how they do behave (descriptive).’

GENDER EQUITY IN CHINA

Gender inequality is still a significant issue in developing countries with variable levels ranging from the highest in the Middle East and Africa, moderate in South Asian countries, and average in the Asia-Pacific and East Asia. Although China is not reported to be among the countries with a low level, it has not been reported as one of the countries establishing ‘women-only’ universities—yet they have done so (e.g., China Women’s University, established in 1949), according to Lee (as cited in Neubauer et al., 2013, pp. 166). Taking this into account, the segregation of females and males has been a controversial issue. While some countries regard the equal provision of services to females as achieving equality—regardless of females being separated from males—other countries argue that equality can be achieved only through integration of both females and males. The latter believe that this establishes a covert pattern of discrimination as competition between females and males will be unfair, as quotas are used to distribute jobs, services, and so on.

In China, ‘the appearance of public schools for girls during the last decade of the Qing dynasty represents one of the most dramatic social and cultural changes of the period’ (Bailey, 2007, p. 34). The first admission of Chinese girls to universities was in 1919 and the first girls’ school was founded in 1998 (Bailey, 2007). Liu and Carpenter (2005) assert ‘women did not become part of the mainstream education system until the last sixty years’ due to the Confucian ideology (p. 266), and only ‘when the entire population becomes conscious about gender discrimination and willing to share wealth, power, and opportunity, women’s education will be accomplished to its full extent’ (p. 280). Historically, certain ethnic groups were discriminated against in China, such as the ‘Kazakhs in Xinjiang, China,’ according to Hakim (as cited Joseph, 2007, p. 235) or were generally treated as goods for selling and slavery throughout the country, until 1949, when it became illegal internationally, according to Reid (as cited in Joseph, 2007, p. 504). Mission schools were themselves enhancing the traditional view of women as housewives and ‘the primary motivation for establishing these early schools was to train girls to serve as the future wives of Chinese pastors.’ If not, they were then religiously biased, leading to a social parity in a society such as China where religion has no role to play ‘... as Bible women’ (Bailey, 2007, p. 13). Additionally, Lear accounted for the impact of girls’ education in north China at protestant mission schools between 1872 and 1924 which is described as ‘leave[ing] a lasting impression on education for girls in China’ (2009, p. ii).

RESEARCH ON GENDER EQUITY: A CHINESE PERSPECTIVE

Much research has been conducted on the equity of female education worldwide. Much research has been conducted into female education inequity in China—describing it as ‘gendered’ (Zhang, 2009, p. i) and procedurally yet substantively practised (Wang, 2016). This review synthesises gender inequity in China and is presented across seven themes which contribute positively or negatively to gender inequity in education. These themes are: gender equity and minorities; gender equity in higher and vocational educations; national development and policy adjustment; Chinese context-based social factors; misconceptualisation of gender equity; quantitative inequity; and finally, mission schools and some other impacting factors.

First, several studies claim that gender inequity in education could be attributed to social discrimination against minorities in China. That said, for minorities in China, and especially for minority females, access to education is reduced and of a lower quality (e.g., Tibet, Lahu, Lisu, and Hani) (Minority-Nationalities, 1995) and distribution of female education is unequal, with preference to coastal areas, creating a gap between eastern and western China (Qiao, 2003) in general, and rural and urban areas in particular (Li, 2014). Further, it is reported that there is an uneven distribution of educational institutions based on family background (Zheng, 2004) and religious aspects, such as Muslim girls' education (Zhang, 2012). Although these studies provided some evidence for the claim to gender inequality in the education system, they remain questionable as most of them were based on either interviews or opinion surveys for small populations in China. In other words, considering the large size of the population in China, the generalisability chance remains very weak. More importantly yet epistemologically, subjectivity as a tool of knowledge has less trustworthiness.

Second, many researchers assume that gender education inequity is remarkably observed in higher education and vocational education. There is a need to develop female higher education institutions as compared to developed countries (Shi, 2006), and there is a shortage of materials promoting and teaching education of gender roles to female college girls towards concrete realisation and integration of 'gender education with political and professional education' (Yu, 2016, p. 53). Besides, there is a need to decrease depression and enhance readiness and [innovation] for female college students in Tianjin majoring in 'pharmaceutical preparation techniques talents' (Liu et al., 2016, p. 77). More importantly, 'education equality' and as an 'aspect of education democratisation' can be realised not only by providing equal access to education but also equal opportunities and interaction between students and education institutions (On education equality, 2003, pp. 2–3). Education policies should use available theories like the Human Capital Theory and Theory of Higher Education Cost Share to approach the 'impovertised students' who fail to access higher education and affordable tuition fees (Yu, 2005, p. 72). With this in mind, we need 'sustainable development of college girl students' through raising awareness of 'self-esteem, self-confidence, self-dependence, and self-reliance' in the universities (Liu, 2013, p. 127) just as seen in the reports on the psychological pressure for college girls in vocational education (Yu, 2015a). In particular, it is important in vocational education to deliberately not pay attention to gender differences between the two sexes (Hong, 2017). The above studies have therefore mostly supported their claims for the existence of a gendered education system with outputs based on examining abstract concepts (e.g., confidence, awareness, etc.) or on the fact that there are fewer female students in medicine and science. These views are again very argumentative but by themselves cannot stand to claim that science education is selective as there is no clear policy, at least to make it procedural and systematic. Put differently, trying to achieve a balanced world based on gender hinders the development of any country. Although there might indeed be gendered practices, these studies focused and directed their findings towards reaching total equity—ignoring the importance of quality that needs to be considered, regardless of gender.

Third, some studies linked the achievement of equal female education to the nation's national development. Building upon this objective, it is assumed that working towards women's liberation could result in a powerful and more potent nation (Yen Fu as cited in Xue, 2015), providing that this would be a national target objective (Xu, 2016). Not surprisingly, some research would describe China as 'relatively backward' compared to the rest of the world, with a need for constitutional legislation which regulates gender discrimination in employment (Wu, 2014, p. 3) and provision for equality in the learning environment (Sun, 2011). Although China's female education has been moving from feudalism to modern China, 'i.e., the Hui ethnic female education system,' this specification has been limited to an imitative version of the full realisation of female education due to social barriers (So, 2017, p. 204).

The rise of female education has impacted the national development of the nation (Zhu, 2013), including a noticeable change between female education in the late Qing Dynasty period and the early republican period, although a [new] trend has started in female education challenges (Liu, 2002). Undoubtedly, the development of the nation is linked to the development of girls' education where [total] literacy should at least be achieved through the policy of nine years of compulsory education, as an initial intervention (Liang, 2008) equal in importance to the parents' education (He, 2016). At any rate, a few papers acknowledge that female education has been progressing but still needs further development to match the national development of the country (Li, 2010) as well as a specific policy regarding gender bias, namely male-biased sex as in the one-child policy applied to Han Chinese only (Li et al., 2011). Collectively, it seems to be inconsistent with operating policies such as the recently terminated one-child policy—except for rural areas—to be replaced with a two-child policy, in addition to some studies reporting the abortion of females. Still, the above output remains arguable. There might be several reasons related to socio-cultural issues, but in general, there is not a clear male-biased policy, including in leadership. For one reason or another, the above studies overestimated extremism in female role-following, just as with extremism in male role-following! Having all eligible human capital in work and being *productive* is the ultimate aim of any country, but putting one gender over the other leads invariably to an offensive cycle of arguments about penis envy and womb envy (i.e., Freudian psychoanalytic theory concerning the sexual stages of child development).

Fourth, gender inequality in education might be attributed to social factors unique to the Chinese context. That being said, education in China is described as a socio-based system marked with easy access to the majority of women (Min, 2013) with women having taken over two thousand years to reach [emancipation], coupled with a sense of equality as its social essence (Nie & Ma, 2011). Not surprisingly, to read that female moral education was improbably viewed in the age of the Ming Dynasty as guided by the principle of 'keeping the justice and killing the human desire' (Liu, 2017, p. 72), as opposed to the need to promote 'community female education' towards supporting adult women's education (Jia & Yang, 2015, p. 19). Above all, the educational gap in equality can exist not only between rural and urban areas, east and west, male and female—at the macro level but even at a micro level, i.e., female and female (e.g., southern Jiangsu and northern Jiangsu) (Wang, 2011)—but also through son to daughter preference or vice versa (e.g., Shanxi province) (Robinson, 2012; Zhou, 2012). Again, the above output gave evidence of China's cultural and social bases, ignoring the remarkable efforts that have been taking place to reach an equal education system—one that does not affect the quality over equality. It might be biased to judge the Chinese education system in these ways, but it is certainly unequal! When approaching this view at the macro level and comparing it to the western world, it will undoubtedly manifest several shortcomings. On the other hand, when it is compared to other Asian countries, as well as Arab and other countries, these shortcomings shrink, and there is value in an in-depth analysis of gender and education in a particular country.

Fifth, a misconception of female education and gender equity in China is another controversy supporting the view of [gendered] education in China (e.g., female education, girls' education, women's education, maternal education, etc.) (Xiong, 2015). The fact that female education is wrongly misconceptualised (Wang & Jiang, 2013) is merged with the dilemma of applying [gender equality], both in China and the West (Wang, 2006). For that reason, there is a need to improve 'independent consciousness' of primary and secondary school female education to ensure awareness of their problems (Jia & Wang, 2015, p. 81), and this should be through promoting a 'Chinese feminist movement', guided by post-modern feminism (Liu, 2011, p. 1). This could be supported with insights from Roble and Martin's gender development theory of 'gender role education' and 'gender equality awareness education' (Wang et al., 2009, p. 235). Aside from that, other factors that increase inequity in

female education include the 'misapplication' of the concept of (education for women) with subjective approaches to explore the problems in women's education, without referring to the Chinese context (Liang, 2003, p. 38), as well as a lack of awareness about gender education along with the absence of practical implementation and a balance between theory and practice (Ge & Qin, 2015). Given this, what is needed is the promotion of a 'harmonious and stable development of family and society' through 'scientific gender education' (Mu & Han, 2017, p. 31) and 'gender-sensitive education' that takes into account the traditional gender education inherited from the Confucius era (Yao & Wang, 2013). The above views seem to be either directly or indirectly influenced by *feminism*. In one way or another, there is a subjective call for promoting female education, which is a way to *establish* a gap between female education and [male education]—if it even exists.

Sixth, a few studies with more credible findings based on quantitative results (e.g., China General Social Survey: CGSS) also reviewed China's [gendered] education. For instance, a study of the urban labour market reported the occurrence of four gender discrimination variables (i.e., education, experience, health, and mothers' education) (Zhao, 2015), and another reported discrimination in hourly wages according to experience, marital status, ownership, health and, above all, in employment (Zhao, 2014). Moreover, another study using the Chinese General Social Survey (CGSS)-2010 data recorded two forms of gender discrimination: son to daughter preference (male over a female) and between urban and rural regions, eastern and western China with more recorded gaps between urban and rural regions—all could be decreased through the provision of mothers' education (Huang & Zhao, 2016). One more study analysed entrance examination scores of 6782 undergraduates, where females generally outperformed males, but this was not reflected in terms of employment (Cai, 2016). Similarly, it was found that ordinary least square (OLS) 'estimates of the economic returns to education for men are slightly higher than those for women' and instrumental variable (IV) 'estimates for women are higher than for men' (Guifu & Hamori, 2009, p. 151). Interestingly, this inequity could even occur in homework self-regulation in school education (Hong et al., 2009), and rank and income (Gustafsson & Sai, 2009). Additionally, discrimination was reported in health (i.e., obesity prevention) (Aitsi-Selmi et al., 2013) and household assets (mainly in rural China) (Deng et al., 2014). Finally, a study reported a lower return rate in female engineering education than males (Fan & Zhang, 2015). Among all the above-reviewed themes and their findings, this theme, in particular, seems to have plausible reasoning and logical contribution describing female education inequity, although the results remain questionable and hardly generalisable.

Seventh, gender education in China has been impacted by mission schools and other external influencing factors. Several studies attributed the development of female education in China to female church schools since the reform movement in 1898 (Zhang, 2016). Although purely Christian-based, mission schools led to the liberation of Chinese women and the rise of female education (Wang, 2013). In addition, girls' mission schools immensely helped to emancipate Chinese women and released them from what was known as 'the female's virtue is to not have any talent' (Zhu, 2004, p. 69). The influence of Japanese education had also played a role in female education in China, mainly with the principle of 'dutiful wife and loving mother' as in traditional Japanese female education (Xu et al., 2013, p. 116). This development has gone through multidimensional levels: space, time and context merged with the 'unique setting of China' (Yang, 2010, p. 5) and the rise of 'modern women's education' in China compared to 'western women's education' (Yan, 2000) in particular in the US (Zhang, 2013). Furthermore, leading thinkers such as Liang Qichao called for equal education opportunities for both females and males (Zhou, 2013) and expansion of the honourable tradition by certain families (e.g., Zheng's family, Pujiang, Zhejiang province), who adapted three principles: daughter, wife, and mother (Dong, 2015, p. 72). This theme examined missionary education—valued in some studies and criticised in others, attributing this to religious and

political reasons. In all cases, the above findings again support the view that female education inequity cannot be easily judged as procedural and systematic even if it merely exists as supported by the studies mentioned above.

Overall, this systematic review challenges the claim of the gendered education system and attempts to reach a different conclusion about the status of female education in China. However, the above literature contained a review of 50 studies conducted by Chinese researchers, supporting the [gendered] education claim. The above review attempted to answer the following questions: what are the examined variables and themes explored by Chinese researchers supporting their views on gender inequity in China? How does this output sound from an analytic perspective? These 50 studies were retrieved from the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) database (<http://oversea.cnki.net/kns55/>). Chinese researchers conducted all the reviewed studies, which could match our study's purposes since we will consider the output of the reviewed studies in our systematic review and whether this output was done by insider or outsider researcher(s). This can help us avoid being biased as well as ignoring the Chinese researchers' voice on this issue to some extent. In short, the review of such studies resulted in generating seven themes—representing the major topics which have been studied in female education in China. These included: gender equity and minorities, gender equity in higher and vocational education, national development and policy adjustment, context-based social factors in China, misconceptualisation of gender equity, quantitative inequity, and finally, mission schools and some other impacting factors.

Rationale

The above-reviewed studies reported seven patterns supporting the claim of female education being gendered, procedural and a substantive practice in China. First, while the studies evidenced significant discrimination against females who belong to minority ethnic groups in China, the government continues to assert in its current National Plan 2010–2020 that 'the fundamental way to achieve this is to allocate reasonable education resources, give preference to rural, impoverished, remote and border areas as well as ethnic autonomous areas, and to bridge the gap in education development' (Ministry of Education of People's Republic of China, 2010, p. 8).

Similarly, in the second pattern, the reported findings compared their views on biased higher education and vocational education to that of the government, asserting that 'open, equal and competitive approaches will be improved in school and college enrolment' (Ministry of Education of People's Republic of China, 2010, p. 26).

The third pattern of studies linked the country's national development to the failure of achieving [absolute] gender equality. On the other hand, the government states 'we need to step up education on citizenship and establish socialist concepts of democracy, the rule of law, freedom, equality, equity and justice for the students, and turn them into qualified social citizens' (Ministry of Education of People's Republic of China, 2010, p. 10).

The fourth pattern of studies attributed female education inequity to socio-cultural factors that are not dealt with in intervention policies. This again contradicts the National Plan policies where efforts have been put into 'enhancing education on the fine traditions of Chinese culture and revolutionary traditions' through 'moral education' which 'should be incorporated into teaching and learning at schools, at home, and in the society (Ministry of Education of People's Republic of China, 2010, p. 10). The fifth pattern introduced the issue of the multiple and variable use of concepts relating to female education. This has created a confusion to proper understanding of the problems encountering female education. Additionally, studies of the sixth pattern claimed a numerically unbalanced gender education in terms of students,

income, returns, etc. However, the National Plan claims that ‘free compulsory education has become the norm in urban and rural areas’, and ‘remarkable progress has also been made in achieving education equity’ (Ministry of Education of People’s Republic of China, 2010, p. 5). This policy clearly states that ‘equal access to education is a major cornerstone of social justice’ (Ministry of Education of the People’s Republic of China, 2010, p. 8).

Finally, the seventh pattern looked at mission schools and other factors with their positive and negative impacts on female education equity. The National Plan has also made it clear that [modernised] Marxism merged with moral education and political education should remain the source for any related education matters: ‘fostering Marxist outlooks on the motherland, ethnicity, and religion, consolidating the grand unity between people of all ethnic backgrounds, and enhancing national pride and cohesion’ (Ministry of Education of People’s Republic of China, 2010, p. 23).

Given this, it is worth examining these contradictive views regarding the possibility of a more plausible output on female education equity in China. Systematic reviews are recognised as a vital source of rigorously and transparently synthesised information by educational decision-makers. Decision-makers have described a lack of evidence on gender inequity in education as a barrier to using systematic reviews for eliminating gender disparities.

Objectives

In this paper, we examine the claim regarding whether female education in China is gendered and procedurally yet substantively practised or not. We therefore did a systematic review of the quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method design studies on female education equity in China between 2009 and 2020. The selection of this timeline is attributed to the following two reasons. First, the starting data is marked by the year before starting the National Plan 2010–2020 for national education reform. Second, the ending date is also attributed to the last date when this paper was conducted, although some papers appear to be published after 2018 but were still conducted in 2018 as indicated in those papers’ publication information). The authors’ roles included study proposal, selections of studies, review of studies and writing up of the paper by the first author, reviewing whole paper and design by the second author, Turkish language by the third author, and editing by the fourth author. That being said, the present systematic review attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What are the substantive findings of qualitative synthesis on gender equity of female education in China?
2. Regardless of the existence or absence of gender inequity: what patterns of female education exist, and what kind of framework or model could be proposed to reform female education in China?

METHODS

Systematic reviews are not restricted to the health and life sciences, as many people would think. Smith argued that ‘systematic reviews are not inherently medical or scientific—even the medical and scientific ones’ and ‘education is much too important to leave to politicians and chance: evidence-informed education protects and informs all stakeholders and encourages greater political/democratic participation, accountability and responsibility’ (2002, Conclusions). Andrews also emphasised the role of systematic review in education research, mainly concerning policy and practice (2005). Systematic reviews, according to Wright et al.

(2007), are defined as a 'review of the evidence on a formulated question that uses systematic and explicit methods to identify, select and critically appraise relevant primary research, and to extract and analyse data from the studies that are included in the review (Wright et al., 2007). Systematic reviews are characterised by the 'researchers conducting [them] using explicit, systematic methods that are selected with a view aimed at minimising bias, to produce more reliable findings to inform decision-making' (Cochrane Library, 2020, About Cochrane Reviews).

Different researchers and academic institutions have identified several types of systematic reviews. Cochrane identified five Cochrane reviews: intervention, diagnostic test accuracy, methodology, qualitative and prognosis reviews (Cochrane Library, 2020). Grant and Booth identified 14 types of reviews, of which systematic review is described as 'the best-known type of review ... seek[ing] to systematically search for, appraise and synthesise research evidence' (2009, p. 102). A few databases for reporting systematic reviews, primarily for healthcare sciences, including the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, PROSPERO, and The Campbell Collaboration, have a multidiscipline scope for systematic reviews education (Ryerson University, 2019, Sep 6, Systematic Reviews).

There are a few standard guidelines for conducting systematic reviews. For instance, 'PRISMA is an evidence-based minimum set of items for reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses,' and it 'focuses on the reporting of reviews evaluating randomised trials, but can also be used as a basis for reporting systematic reviews of other types of research, particularly evaluations of interventions' (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses [PRISMA], 2015). And authors use PRISMA to 'improve the reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses' (PRISMA, 2015). The University of Wollongong, Australia introduced four tools that can be used to develop and report a systematic review, mainly PROSPERO, PRISMA, PICO framework, and SPIDER (2019, October 11, Systematic Review). We used the general guideline for systematic reviews on PRISMA (<http://www.prisma-statement.org>), modified to match our education study. Our report included the 27 items identified in the PRISMA checklist and the flow diagram. However, we added an introduction before the rationale and objectives. Also, we used the SPIDER tool for the data extraction instead of Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, (Study type) PICO(S) (i.e., this tool is detailed below in the data collection process).

Validity and reliability of systematic reviews are approached by following the PRISMA criteria and the selected tool, namely SPIDER, here (Liberati et al., 2009; Pati & Lorusso, 2018; Thompson et al., 2012). Table A2 on Appendix 2 illustrates how the 27 items of PRISMA are included in this paper. In addition, the thick description of each section of this systematic review enhances this paper's trustworthiness. In short, this paper ensures *conformity* by following the exact steps prescribed in the PRISMA checklist. *Credibility* is also approached by reviewing screened studies by an independent researcher and being transparent in describing all the reviewed studies' details. The findings' dependability is also ensured because they are descriptive based on the analysis, and inferential based on the used theory and generated data. The detailed reporting of all the steps followed and the results is also an attempt towards achieving *transferability*. *Transparency* is also achieved by providing the same year's detailed description of the design of the study. Finally, the reported findings and model are assumed to be close to the truth of female education in China—hopefully reaching a high level of *validity*.

Protocol and registration

This review does not have an officially registered protocol, but all the review steps, processes and guidelines were specified and documented ahead. However, a few changes

have been made that need to be reported here. First, there was no intention to integrate a theory into the review. However, we later realised that this would increase the validity of the output (i.e., the practical theory is incorporated into the discussion part to generate a female education model and to reform female education). One study was also added after extracting the 46 eligible studies' data, to become 47 (i.e., Alduais et al., 2020). This study was added for its vitality and immediate relevance to the present study.

Eligibility criteria

Studies eligible for inclusion—either quantitatively, qualitatively, or both—examined the equity and development of female education in China and collected data between 2009–present. The exclusion criteria were output for the inclusion criteria. Put differently, after title screening, 85 studies were selected as long as they included female education (development) in China; women education (development) in China; gender education (development) in China; gender discrimination (development) in China; girls education (development) in China; gender equality/equity in China; gender inequality/inequity in China; and were in/included mainland China (i.e., others not mentioned clearly in the title). The abstract screening was conducted to reach more specific studies based on data between 2009–present, were in/included mainland China (i.e., not Hong Kong, Macau, etc.), publication information (not received before 2009 as this would undoubtedly mean the collected data is before 2009), and full paper (i.e., not reviews, short commentaries, etc.).

Information sources

In January 2018, we searched Google Scholar, SAGE, EBSCO, Science Direct, Proquest Education, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global A & I: The Humanities and Social Sciences Collection, Scopus and Taylor and Francis—linked via Beijing Normal University Online Database for articles on female education equity in China between (2009–present). We restricted our research language to English and fully published papers, theses and dissertations. It was mentioned in the introduction that female education is an over-researched area—justifying the limitation of the research language to English. For the same reason, only fully published sources were selected. Another reason is to keep controlling the extracted data quality—matching the PRISMA criteria and the SPIDER criteria for the included studies' characteristics (see Table A1 of the synthesis of evidence and results section mainly).

Search

We defined female education equity to include all conceptually related terms (i.e., gender disparity, gender disparities, gender gap, differences between the sexes, gender difference, sex difference, gender mainstreaming, the gap between the sexes, gender-neutral, gender-sensitive, gender-specific, inequalities between men and women and gender-based disparities). Moreover, we defined female education development as educational issues related to female education levels: preschool education, primary school, junior middle school, senior middle school, vocational education, special education, higher education, vocational education and distance education.

Search terms included female education in China, gender education in China, gender equity in China, gender equality, women education in China, girls education in China, education discrimination in China, and education equality in China. We limited the research to

articles that included the title's full search terms, minimising the results. To avoid missing any articles, we used different databases, although only a few articles were added; many were therefore duplicated.

Study selection and data collection process

Two researchers extracted the data, including the first author who designed the data extraction form (see synthesis evidence Table A1). We reviewed three tools of research PICO, PICOS and SPIDER (Cooke et al., 2012; Methley et al., 2014), and we decided to use the last one because it matched our research approach, using quantitative, qualitative and mixed research articles. The first author and the second independent researcher extracted the data (i.e., both researchers hold PhDs in comparative education with particular education majors, policy analysis for former and higher education and policy analysis for the latter). The two forms (i.e., referring to the synthesis evidence Table A1, Appendix 1) were compared, and significant differences were found in the amount of extracted data for the findings. The results column was finalised based on the researchers' agreement to include the study's significant finding, which described the status of female education.

Data items

The eligible studies matched the extraction sheet, which included ten columns: the first five represent the number of the study, source, date of publication, researcher identity and setting, and the second five represent the SPIDER tool (i.e., Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation and Research type).

Risk of bias in individual studies

To ascertain the validity of the included studies, the SPIDER tool was used, and the studies during the extraction were reviewed by one independent researcher and the first author, based on the five factors of the SPIDER tool, mentioned above.

Summary measures

The current report did not include a meta-analysis. That being said, summary measures in this report were semi-objective. In other words, we attempted to categorise the output of the eligible included studies into three categories: almost total inequality, relative inequality, and almost total equality, based on the reported output for the examined/explored variables in each study.

Synthesis of results

Since objective heterogeneity and consistency among studies were not possible due to the inclusion of variable designs, these were attempted through the criteria guided by the included study sheets' characteristics. The synthesis of the results restricts itself to the extracted data, avoiding further elaboration that might result in either over/inter interpretation of the extracted output.

Risk of bias across studies

The researchers considered publication bias or minor/major finding-extraction issues during data collection and data extraction. None of the studies was excluded or included because of the publication date, as long as it has been published in the specified inclusion period and matched the other inclusion characteristics (i.e., being conducted between 2009 and 2018, even if the publication date is after 2018). Some of the studies were also reported as having significantly more detailed findings in the evaluation column than the other studies. These were modified and reduced to be consistent with others.

Table 1 shows the assessment of the quality of the included studies based on the SPIDER tool. The 47 included studies were assessed as either low, medium, or high quality. These were given based on different criteria. High-quality studies were those which mentioned the date of the publication, authors and their affiliation; the setting of the study is specified clearly; the sample is mentioned and well-explained; the topic of the research is related to education regardless of level; the measures used for data collection are mentioned and explained; a conclusion answering the questions of the study are mentioned; and the research type is indicated and well-justified. On the other hand, low-quality studies were those not giving a date of publication, authors and their affiliation; the setting is not specific and not justified; the sample is not well-defined or not commonly used in research; the topic of the research is about gender equity but not focusing on education, the design does not clearly describe the tools used for data collection; the conclusions are abstract and ambiguous; and the research type is not mentioned or justified well. The last column included medium quality, and this was given for the overall evaluation of each study. A study was rated as high-quality if it does not have any item of the SPIDER tool with low risk, medium-quality when having one item with low risk, and low-quality when having more than one item with low risk.

RESULTS

This section presents the synthesis of the evidence using the characteristics of the included studies. Table A1 in the Appendix 1 shows the extracted data using the SPIDER tool, and below is a synthesis of the extracted evidence.

Study selection

Two thousand and ninety-five titles were identified. Of these ($n = 85$) (i.e., 'n' refers to the number of studies throughout this paper) were included after title screening. It appeared then that only ($n = 59$) were eligible for inclusion after the abstract screening. After full screening and data extraction, it was clear that only ($n = 47$) studies met the SPIDER criteria in addition to not including data before 2009 (i.e., the specified starting date for our analysis). Given this, ($n = 13$) studies were excluded from inclusion in the systematic review (Figure 1).

STUDY CHARACTERISTICS

Publication date

The included studies were conducted (i.e., one paper is published in 2020 but met the criterion of being conducted between 2009 and 2018, when this systematic review was conducted)

TABLE 1 Assessment of the quality of the included studies using the SPIDER Tool

Study	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of Interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type	Overall Quality
Study 1	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 2	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 3	😊	😊	😞	😞	😞	😊	😊	😊	😞
Study 4	😊	😊	😞	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😞
Study 5	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 6	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 7	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 8	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 9	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 10	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 11	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 12	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 13	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 14	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 15	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 16	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 17	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 18	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 19	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 20	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 21	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 22	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 23	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 24	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 25	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 26	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 27	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 28	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 29	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 30	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 31	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 32	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 33	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 34	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 35	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 36	😊	😊	😊	😞	😞	😊	😊	😊	😞
Study 37	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 38	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 39	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 40	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 41	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 42	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 43	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 44	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 45	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 46	😊	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
Study 47	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊

😊Low Risk; 😞High Risk; 😞Unclear Risk.

between 2009 and 2018 with no paper submitted before 2009. This violates our criteria for assessing data between 2009–present. Given this, the frequency order for the included studies according to the date of publication was: (2009: $n = 1/47$), (2010: $n = 6/47$), (2011: $n = 3/47$), (2012: $n = 9/47$), (2013: $n = 5/47$), (2014: $n = 9/47$), (2015: $n = 5/47$), (2016: $n = 6/47$), (2017: $n = 2/47$) and (2018: $n = 1/47$). These criteria are linked to the National Plan 2010–2020 (Ministry of Education of People's Republic of China, 2010), regarding the realisation of this policy until now. Papers published/submitted earlier than 2009 but published online in/after 2009 were excluded (see synthesis evidence Table A1 for the included studies).

FIGURE 1 Synthesis evidence flow diagram

Researcher identity

We categorised the researchers in the extracted data as insiders (i.e., Chinese researchers), outsiders (non-Chinese researchers), outside insiders (Chinese abroad), and inside outsiders (non-Chinese in China). This classification was determined based on the reported affiliation in the publications. The data extraction and analysis extraction resulted in a fifth category: mixed researchers of either two or more of the four primary classifications. Of these, the highest frequency of the studies was done by mixed identities of researchers ($n = 21/47$), insiders ($n = 11/47$), outside insiders ($n = 9/47$), outsiders ($n = 6/47$), and ($n = 0/47$) for inside outsiders.

Setting

‘Remarkable progress has also been made in achieving education equity’ (Ministry of Education of People’s Republic of China, 2010, p. 5) and ‘the fundamental requirement of education equity is that all citizens have equal rights to receive education according to the law’ (p. 8). With this in mind and our objective of examining female education equality and

development throughout China, we considered the setting of the included studies as part of the systematic review themes. The studies seemed to represent almost all of China, where 16 studies were based on nationwide data, with others having different settings, including schools and universities. Also, several studies mentioned the setting of rural China (e.g., Maimaiti & Siebert, 2009), rural regions (e.g., Maslak, 2011), western China (e.g., Gong et al., 2014, and eastern China (e.g., Yu & Xie, 2010).

Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type (SPIDER)

Sample

We identified nine major categories for sampling in the 47 included studies (see Appendix 1, Table A1, for the extracted synthesis evidence). These included: students (i.e. basic education and higher education) ($n = 18,424$), staff ($n = 458$), schools ($n = 203$), higher education institutions ($n = 66$), rural villages and households ($n = 150$), families and parents ($n = 95$), community people ($n = 7189$), and reviewed literature and census data. Of these studies ($n = 14$) were based on census data, ($n = 3$) reviewed literature, and the rest on various populations from the categories mentioned above.

Phenomenon of interest

All of the 47 studies included accounted for education equality in China; studies where other gender factors did not consider education equality were excluded. The examined phenomena of interest varied from purely educational issues (e.g., student enrolment, cognition, teacher biases, leadership roles, etc.) to those linking other factors (e.g., health, social structure, income, employment, etc.) as being impacted by education equality.

Design

The analysis of the included studies resulted in seven categories of measures. These included: (online) survey/questionnaire ($n = 10$), (online) interviews ($n = 11$), census data, reviewed studies or both ($n = 18$), a mixture of surveys, interviews, observations and census data ($n = 3$), tests ($n = 1$), experiments ($n = 2$), ethnographic studies and case profiles ($n = 2$).

Evaluation

The reported findings of the 47 included studies were divided into three types, as shown in Table 2 below—the criteria for deciding which one consists of the authors' strictly reported findings and the findings' wording. In cases where the results were a mixture of the three types, they were written in all the relevant columns (e.g., study 44).

Research type

The data was extracted with five predetermined research approaches (i.e., Survey, Experimental, Correlational, Case Study, and Ethnographic Study), where the first three are

TABLE 2 Female education equity patterns based on the systematic review

Almost total inequality	Almost relative inequality	Almost equal
Specific learning environment services ⁽¹⁾	Effective integration in educational management ⁽³⁾	Searching for freedom in urban China ⁽⁸⁾
Policies ⁽²⁾	Leadership role improvement ⁽⁵⁾	Bt cotton performance among farmers ⁽¹²⁾
Cultural reasons ⁽⁴⁾	Son preference and selective abortion ⁽¹¹⁾	Impacting modern depressive disorder ⁽¹⁷⁾
Contribution to education ⁽⁶⁾	Payoff and wages ⁽¹³⁾	Cheating among students: forms and reasons ⁽²²⁾
Urban-rural China in higher education ⁽⁷⁾	Academics and stereotypes ⁽¹⁴⁾	Education impacting health ⁽³⁰⁾
Empowerment concept ⁽⁹⁾	Different factors including education ⁽¹⁶⁾	+Cognition ability ⁽³²⁾
Majority of men in the socialist regime ⁽¹⁰⁾	Empowering women in higher education ⁽²¹⁾	Body mass index ⁽³⁴⁾
Teacher treatment ⁽¹⁵⁾	Digital inequality in home and school, urban and rural areas ⁽²⁴⁾	K12 social-emotional wellbeing ⁽³⁸⁾
Self-employment rates ⁽¹⁸⁾	Educational attainment, level-based ⁽²⁵⁾	Public education ⁽⁴⁴⁾
Cultural capital: parents' roles ⁽¹⁹⁾	Suicide ratio varying between urban and rural for females ⁽²⁷⁾	+Females' performance in economic education, effort ⁽⁴²⁾
Payment differences ⁽²⁰⁾	Mothers' involvement in children's achievement ⁽²⁹⁾	Higher numbers of females in some variables, a higher number of males in some variables, and insignificant differences between males and females form a large number of variables among 76 examined indicators ⁽⁴⁷⁾
Traditional gender roles ⁽²⁶⁾	Female math education ⁽³³⁾	
Women's voice ⁽²⁸⁾	Income, ethnic ⁽⁴⁰⁾	
Human capital rate ⁽³¹⁾	Further understanding of unique female features ⁽⁴³⁾	
Exclusion of urban females in higher education ⁽³⁵⁾	Gender stereotypes for men employed on Early Childhood Teachers (ECTs) ⁽⁴⁵⁾	
Self-perceived health perceptions such as son preference ⁽³⁶⁾	Varying perspectives of Chinese Muslims impacted by globalisation and modernisation ⁽⁴⁶⁾	
Systematic discrimination with resistance ⁽³⁷⁾		
Inequality of opportunity, ethnic ⁽³⁹⁾		
Public health care and pension ⁽⁴⁴⁾		
Vocational education, practical involvement in leadership and decision making ⁽³⁷⁾		

considered as quantitative research and the last two as qualitative research. Of these, our analysis was based on the measures used, analysis, and presentation of the data indicated quantitative-based papers ($n = 27$), qualitative-based papers ($n = 17$), and mixed-method ($n = 3$). Although several papers reported quantitative and qualitative measures in nature,

the data analysis and presentation of information were qualitative. Hence, they were not written as mixed-method research. The research type column in Table A1 shows the studies in the three major types: quantitative, qualitative or mixed.

Risk of bias within studies

As mentioned in the methods section, the data extraction sheet and the SPIDER tool helped decrease the risk of bias within studies. Besides, in the flow diagram, it has been mentioned that 13 studies were excluded because they did not meet the criteria of the SPIDER tool. In other words, initially, 59 studies were selected for inclusion, but after applying the SPIDER criteria, they failed to meet these fully.

Results of individual studies

Each study's extracted findings are summarised in Table 2, mainly from the evaluation column and using three categories: almost total inequality in female education, relative inequality, and relative equality. See also Table A1 for a more detailed evaluation.

Synthesis of results

Generally speaking, there is no separate section in the National Plan 2010–2020 specified for gender education equity/inequity. However, concerning the quotations we mentioned in the rationale section, indicative words like *equity*, *equal education*, *education for all citizens*, etc., have been repeated frequently throughout this policy document's content. Our literature review in the introductory section identified six significant themes/factors/areas manifesting female education equity in China. These included gender equity and minorities; gender equity in higher and vocational educations; national development and policy adjustment; Chinese context-based social factors; misconceptualisation of gender equity; quantitative inequity; and finally, mission schools and some other factors.

Our systematic review also included similar and new themes/factors that still manifest female education (in)equity in China, although over eight years have passed since the National Plan's enforcement. These included minority discrimination, rural vs. urban areas discrimination, the impact of education on health and psychology, educational leadership and policy, educational attainment/performance, social capital, and various other issues.

Interestingly, one of the significant themes reported in the literature review, namely mission schools, did not appear in any of the included studies in the systematic review. Although the role of mission schools is vanishing, albeit visibly, we still believe that this factor plays a significant role in China's female education. The studies by (Zhu, 2004; Zhang, 2016; Wang, 2013) discussed the impact of mission schools on the rise of female education equity since the 19th century. This theme was not duplicated in the data extracted from the systematic review, but to the authors' knowledge and based on their work experience in the country for the last four years, mission schools do still exist and play a significant role in provoking female education inequity as a trending issue (i.e., research-based evidence is worth considering to examine this belief).

Additionally, two reported studies allowed for confirmation regarding a social phenomenon in the education sector. The study by Xu and Waniganayake (2017) reported possible discrimination against males in early childhood education where two common stereotypes occur in this area. First, society may not accept or may denigrate that males should teach in

early childhood education; and second, this sector should be restricted to females as they seem to be [more qualified] in this area. This has negative indications for females as they are allocated the roles of a mother or housewife, both sharing the responsibility of child care. The study by Alduais et al. (2020) also indicated quantitatively that education personnel in early childhood education between 2009 and 2015 is predominantly females.

Further, Alduais et al. (2020) conducted a secondary analysis using census bureau data for seven years to measure the female education development concerning the National Plan—claiming that female education equity is relative, albeit overt, and covert patterns of female education inequity might necessarily exist. In that study, the researchers challenged the view that female education inequity in China could be gendered and procedurally yet substantively practised. The reported findings in this systematic review refute this claim and highlight some issues that have not been sorted out on the National Plan. However, the conclusions reported in this systematic review, which were primarily based on qualitative designs as compared to the results which refuted the claim of gendered education, which were based on quantitative designs—again put the possibility of claiming that female education equity is relative and should never be assumed or approached as an absolute one.

Risk of bias across studies

The eligible included studies in this report are neither epistemologically, theoretically, nor methodologically consistent and heterogeneous. Since we did not conduct a meta-analysis, this was the first motif to consider variable studies' inclusion. However, the examined variables and the objectives that focused on gender equality and female education were the primary base to bring these studies towards consistency and heterogeneity.

Discussion: Summary of evidence

This study's central assumption was that female education equity should be relative anywhere, and the claims of the existence of a procedural yet substantive practice of female education inequity are too abstract. The literature review indicated six themes incorporating the female education discussion and research for the Chinese researchers based on the most extensive Chinese database (CNKI) research. These themes included gender equity and minorities; gender equity in higher and vocational education; national development and policy adjustment; Chinese context-based social factors; misconceptualisation of gender equity; quantitative inequity; and finally, mission schools and some other factors. In most cases, these studies supported the gendered and procedural yet substantive practice of female education inequity in China. The systematic review attempted to refute this claim or find more reasonable *truths* on the reality of female education inequity in China. However, most of the reviewed studies indicated the existence of inequity (see Table 2); the overall research allowed for the generation of three patterns on the current state of female education.

To start with the comparison between themes, the systematic review reported similar themes to those reviewed in the literature. These included minority discrimination (the minority ethnicities in China are controversial, and the gap is not only in terms of female education but generally, and this interprets the purpose of providing one particular section in the National Plan 2010–2020 to speed up bridging the gaps between minorities and the rest of the country), rural vs. urban areas discrimination (more violations are perpetrated against females in rural vs urban areas), the impact of education on health and psychology (women are believed to receive smaller pensions and fewer rights, especially in terms of maternity

and menstrual cycle), and educational leadership and policy (men occupy almost all prominent leadership positions concerning education, beginning with the Minister of Education, deputy ministers, chancellors, etc.). The first pattern of studies reported that females and males do not have the same rights in several sectors (e.g., the majority of men in the socialist regime, learning environment, teacher treatment, etc.). The second pattern reported relative inequity in preference for sons, math education, leadership roles, etc. The third pattern indicated equal rights in some issues such as cognitive ability, searching for freedom in urban China, etc.

To understand the patterns above better, we attempted using the practical theory (hereafter PT). The primary purpose is to establish a framework that can bring the generated patterns together so that policymakers, decision-makers, and researchers can have a deeper understanding and more precise map to utilise the output of this systematic review for their future needs.

The PT has been introduced by several researchers in different contexts, of which Cronen (1994) asserted that 'practical theory, as distinct from applied theory, is based on the notion of inquiry developed in human systems' research and pragmatism' (2001, p. 14). Cronen describes practical theories in the following way: 'They are developed to make human life better. They provide ways of joining in social activities to promote (a) socially useful description, explanation, critique, and change in situated human action; and (b) emergence of new abilities for all parties involved' (1995, p. 231). Cronen maintained that 'the four primary criteria are whether a theory is useful for (1) identifying a situation-in-view, (2) constructing judgements (systemic hypotheses) about the situation that (3) implicate actions leading to (4) the consequence of improving the situation' (2001, p. 29).

Unlike Cronen, both Goldkuhl and Röstlinger (1999, 2002, 2003, 2006) established PT on their research, starting with proposing studies on the Practice Theory and Work Practice Theory, which were used to propose another form of the PT. In this regard, Goldkuhl asserts, 'initially it [practice theory] was called Theory of Practice, later on, it has been labeled Work Practise Theory. This Theory describes and conceptualises work practices as constellations of actors, actions and action objects (conditions/results)' (2006, p. 1). He continued, '... a practical theory can be any theory as long it is practical and valuable for use. 'Practical' is an attribute we can designate to a theory. We call a theory a practical theory if it serves practical purposes' (2006, p. 3). Goldkuhl wanted to contribute a more specific and productive theory *for generating practical knowledge*—stating, '... there is also a need to specify its [the PT] possible constituents to help people to develop and evaluate practical theories' and '... after working with (developing, applying) practical theories for several years ... I want to contribute with the following specification of its possible (partially overlapping) constituents' (2007, p. 140). Goldkuhl claims that what could be considered a practical theory is '... a kind of instrument for practitioners struggling to manage and improve their practices.

A practical theory may also be an appropriate instrument for conducting practical inquiries, thus informing researchers as well as practitioners' (2008a, p. 8). The author presents a model applying this theory for e-government—arguing that the PT can epistemologically enhance any research with practical output (Goldkuhl, 2008b). With more efforts to support the PT, the author also introduced another model by applying the PT to Information Systems Actability Theory (ISAT), using the five constituents: conceptualisation, patterns, normative criteria, design principles, and models (Goldkuhl, 2009).

We extended our analysis to the theoretical level, mainly using the PT—proposing a model to approach this conflict. The model presents the female education inequity conflict based on five constituents of the PT as proposed (Goldkuhl, 2006, 2007) (see Table 3). These five constituents include conceptualisations, patterns, normative criteria, design principles and models. According to this theory, anything that results in something productive and valuable

would be considered practical. Hereby, practicality is based on productivity, value, and usefulness. Our presented model attempts to introduce a pattern of female education equity that could be practical regarding the National Plan and the systematic review results (Figure 2).

Conceptualisations

We used several concepts to present our model for female education equity/inequity conflict. To make the concepts more specific to our context, we will define each concept here briefly. First, we used 'education' to refer to educational attainment and levels, educational population and personnel. Educational attainment refers to the areas of education, starting with pre-school education and ending with correctional education. The educational population relates to pupils in the school, students in the colleges and universities, and young researchers at the post-doctorate level. Educational personnel is divided into leaders, including administrative personnel and academic staff. In the centre of the model, we used gender, indicating female to male differences. We also used overt (+) versus covert (-) gender: the former includes situations, such as the number of female students in university A being identical to the number of the male students in the same university; the latter contains males occupying situations such as three-quarters of the leadership positions in university A, but the number of the female teachers in the same university is three times the number of male teachers. In addition, we used the symbols (=) to indicate equity and (#) to indicate inequity.

Further, we presented biological differences such as man vs. woman to indicate biological features, and father vs. mother to indicate associations with these biological and physiological features. Simultaneously, we introduced social features that could be social facts as the first two and stereotypes as the second two. Another two concepts are relativism as opposed to extremism. Relativism refers to situations where the education system does not consider or issue any specific gender policies. Hence, equity/inequity is (not) automatically realised.

On the other hand, extremism occurs when there are either overt gender policies against or favouring a specific gender, or exaggerating roles of a particular type of gender. Moreover, the concept policy was introduced with two kinds: general policy vs. specific policy. Policy in this model refers to any policy document, and it could be broad, such as the National Plan 2010–2020, or specific, if it states particular policies for any gender type (e.g., increasing the number of female teachers in maths, increasing the number of female deans, increasing the number of female rectors, etc.). Finally, we introduced six types of capitals. While cultural and social capital is integrated, the main difference between them is related to factors that impact culture, including educational attainment, habits, traditions and religion, and possibly the political system. Social capital refers to society's structure and social norms, such as house, family, community, village, rural vs. urban areas, etc.

Similarly, both the economic and finance capitals are interrelated: the former refers to the natural resources in our context, and the latter refers to the amount of available money in the market. Human capital refers simply to all professions, skills, and jobs with all their types and specifications. Finally, physical capital refers to machines, technological products, etc.

Patterns

The above model simply presents two patterns of conflict in female education. The first pattern is where female education equity is observed, and it has two forms: overt equity and covert equity. Overt equity means that the number of educational populations in all the fields we mentioned is the same. Policies are considering that the numbers should always

TABLE 3 Constituents of the practical theory (adapted from Goldkuhl, 2006)

Constituent	Elements	Examples	Format/use
Practical theory			
Conceptualisations	Things (actions, processes, actors, thoughts, artefacts, texts, norms), properties, and relations	Categorised concepts, relations between concepts, definitions of categories	Textual or graphical
Patterns	How things (may) work...	Preconditions, enablers, affordances, obstacles, strategies, tactics, actions, states, transitions, consequences, and similar meta-categories	Textual descriptions or graphic models
Normative criteria	The goodness of things	Values	Evaluation design of practices
Design principles	How to create good things	Instrumental concerning normative criteria and establishing norms towards betterment	Development of practices
Models	Illustrative crystallisations of a practical theory	Analytic instruments when applying the Theory	Graphic or tabular

be made equal. Covert equity also occurs when all the leadership positions are created to be equal and are shared between females and males. The main difference is that the nature of the positions themselves might not allow absolute equity. For instance, if the Minister of Education is a male, it is illogical to assign another female minister for equity realisation and vice versa. However, the government appoints a female vice-minister position if the minister is a male or vice versa. General and specific policies are functional in this pattern, especially particular policies for bridging gender gaps.

The second pattern is female education inequity, and it has two forms: overt inequity and covert inequity. Overt inequity refers to the situations where the numbers of either gender are significantly higher than the other in any of the listed educational fields, be it for students or education personnel. Covert inequity refers to the situations where males or females dominate leadership positions (e.g., headteachers, chairpersons, managers, etc.) or, more importantly, crucial leadership positions (e.g., deans, rectors, general managers, etc.). Public policies are more functional in this pattern, but specific policies also operate based on cultural and social capital. For instance, religion could affect gender equity and make it systematic and procedural. In Saudi Arabia, particularly for extreme interpretation and over-understanding of the religion, the education policies are gender-biased. In other countries such as Yemen, Oman, Kuwait, UAE, Qatar, Bahrain, there is more flexibility. The gender inequity is more directed by the cultural capital, where there is no specific policy preventing women from doing or studying a particular field. However, society itself plays a significant role in enhancing the tremendous covert gender inequity. This discussion could also extend to other Arab countries where again, the interpretation of the religion impacts gender roles and significant differences between the countries mentioned earlier, and these (e.g., Syria, Lebanon, Morocco, etc.) could take other directions. In comparison, gender inequity in China might have its own aspects, as religion seems ineffective.

Normative criteria

Each of the above patterns, both with two forms, has both positive and negative impacts on the six types of capitals mentioned in the model. The first pattern, namely the overt gender

FIGURE 2 Female education equity model based on the practical theory

equity, theoretically means that all educational and administrative, as well as academic personnel, should be identical. Let us imagine some situations where we will need to increase the number of disabled students to make them quantitatively equal. We will also either need to increase the number of female students or male students to achieve total equity. There will be a need to consider the gender when looking at leadership positions, rather than considering qualifications, skills, and experience. To run this programme, the engineering students will also need to have male/female equity. Similarly, early childhood education will not be viable unless the same numbers of both genders are enrolled.

All these awkward situations may take place due to the extreme interpretation of gender roles and gender equity. Cultural and social capital will manifest a disparity and form gaps in a society which is shaped by an extreme understanding of the gender role. It will, above all, be human capital that will be most affected negatively since equity will be a recruitment standard. This will also reflect negatively on performance in finance, economic and physical capital. These negative impacts could be less harmful in the covert gender equity case, where a specific manipulation occurs in the gender role. The government will attempt to present equal gender roles, but specific policies will make individuals systematically and procedurally biased towards males. This could be achieved through biological and social factors, where women are at a disadvantage to negotiate about them.

The second pattern, covert gender inequity, has more harmful effects and negative impacts on all types of capital. First and foremost, having a high percentage of the general population lacking full education, employment, etc., negatively affects national development. In this regard, the national growth in most Arab, Muslim and African countries is positively impacted due to this disparity between the two genders. The females' social role is overlooked, eliminating other roles that could serve all capital types through educational attainment. It might be less prevalent in countries such as China, but regarding our reviewed studies, different forms of covert gender inequity might occur. This mostly seems to occur in leadership positions or specific education fields. It could also be due to biological factors such as access to water, linked to menarche. All in all, gender parity seems to be problematic when this pattern takes place, be it in the overt or the covert form.

Design principles

Based on the above two patterns, both gender equity and gender inequity are disadvantageous in the short- and the long-term. For this reason, relativism might help to reduce the impact of these two patterns. While cultural and social capital remain primary impacting factors on gender equity in any country, reform should also occur. Relativism could be achieved through reasonable understanding and interpretation of the sources that form cultural and social capitals. It also takes place by preventing the causes of gender gaps. These include over-interpretation and under-interpretation of gender roles, mainly female roles. Gender should never be used as a factor in human capital. Furthermore, this should be reflected in other types of capital.

Models

The above model attempted to present two patterns of gender equity/inequity with pluses and minuses for both of them. This model is significantly impacted and formed by cultural and social capital, which in one way or another, lead researchers to understand and explore which pattern is taking place in a particular country. Any discussion of gender equity without reference to these two types of capitals, in particular, is biased and will be neither practical nor efficient when implemented.

Limitations

Our study has several limitations. First, the included studies were not methodologically consistent, resulting in a semi-objective interpretation of the results. Second, the study did not include a registered systematic review protocol to control the input and the output. One study and the theory analysis were added, but the initial plan did not consider further research nor theory application. Third, some studies have been over-interpreted throughout the report, while some others have been under-interpreted. This situation could have been caused by the researchers' bias towards their proposed assumptions on female education equity in China. It could also be motivated by an interest in the research paper and its relevance to the present study. One primary function of using the systematic review type was to reduce this bias, but its impact *still* remained. Hence, this could be considered a risk of bias within the studies.

Future research

A wise next step should consider the above model through either mixed-method research or several studies of single method research that could be merged later to form a more plausible, credible and valid outcome on the status of female education equity/inequity in China.

CONCLUSION

Forty-seven studies conducted between 2009 and 2020 which examined/explored female education equity in China—including quantitative, qualitative and mixed designs—were reviewed. Most of them indicated gendered and procedural yet substantive female education equity/inequity in China. Although the quantitative studies that were included reported contradictory results refuting this gender inequity pattern, they had evidence of some indicators of gender inequity, at least in the leadership role. The reviewed literature on female education indicated that it is an international phenomenon with variable yet relative differences worldwide. Two central patterns could sum up this issue as overt female education equity versus covert female education equity. This could rephrase as quantitative equity and qualitative equity. While some countries such as the EU struggle to achieve qualitative equity, several other nations such as those in the Middle East are still working with quantitative equity. Caught in the middle between these two forms is equity-like China, in the context of this study. A systematic review of 47 studies of quantitative, qualitative and mixed designs conducted between 2009 and 2020 was conducted to identify the exact patterns of female education in China. The review followed the PRISMA checklist and SPIDER tool to guide the whole research process. The authors also integrated theory with practice, using the Practical Theory with its five constituents (i.e., conceptualisations, patterns, normative criteria, design principles, and model). This theory helped propose a model describing female education's current status in China and reforming female education criteria marked by relativism—achieved by avoiding extremism—overestimating and underestimating gender roles. The essence of this model is also running an education system that excludes the gender factor from several types of capital: cultural, social, human, finance, economic and physical capital. To this end, the following points highlight the contributions of this study:

- The literature review identified some themes: gender equity and minorities, gender equity in higher and vocational education, national development and policy adjustment, Chinese context-based social factors, misconceptualisation of gender equity, quantitative inequity, and finally, mission schools;

- The systematic review identified themes like minority discrimination, rural vs. urban areas discrimination, the impact of education on health and psychology, educational leadership and policy, educational attainment/performance, and social capital;
- The use of the Practical Theory with its five constituents led to a proposed model presenting patterns of female education while at the same time helping to reform it; and
- Policymakers, practitioners and researchers on female education might find it informative and practical to conduct more systematic reviews on female education applying this theory and other related theories.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors and was mainly based on secondary data analysis.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that supports the findings of this study are included in this article as appendix.

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APPENDIX 1

TABLE A1 Synthesis of evidence for female education development in China

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
1	Maimaiti et al.	2009	Outsider(s)	Heilongjiang, Liaoning, Henan, Shangdong, Jiangsu, Hubei, Hunan, Guizhou, and Guangxi	150 rural villages Households	Gender gap related to access to water	Survey	Poor access to water linked to menarche	Quantitative
2	Shiqiong, H. et al.	2010	Outside Insider	China, one university	96 student informants, 134 staff informants	Education, law, and family as factors impacting gender discrimination	Survey	Non-reciprocal influence; education, family then law; traditions and unbalanced policy	Quantitative
3	Wang, X. G.	2010	Insider	China	<i>Virtual managers</i>	Gender equity improvement	Analysis of collected studies	Windmill strategy and interaction of cultural, social, and political context could result in better management beyond the current superficial outputs	Qualitative
4	Yu, L. et al.	2010	Insider	Eastern Mainland China	201 boys, 160 girls 3–6 graders	Gender-age differences, gender identity, and psychological adjustment	Survey	Boys more happy with their gender, they have more pressure on gender stereotypes, cultural differences impact gender identity and concerning psychological adjustment	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
5	Zhong, W. et al.	2010	Mixed	City J, history, culture, outstanding schools	Two female principals, 12 teachers, one supervisor	Female leadership practices: learning & teaching; sources of power	Semi-structured interviews, observations, document analysis	Top-down approach leadership practices	Mixed
6	Yanbi, H. et al.	2010	Insider	China	Reviewed studies and analysis	Education and social stratification: ethnicity, class, and gender	Prior research analysis	Institutional exclusion marked with unequal access to education remains after 30 years reform, men and women might be close in educational attainment, but not for contribution, socioeconomic factors (e.g., ethnicity) still hinder gender equality	Quantitative
7	Xie et al.	2010	Insider	Shaanxi, Fujian, Zhejiang, Hunan, Guangdong, Guangxi, Anhui, Shandong, Shanghai, and Inner Mongolia	50 universities and colleges at ten provinces and urban districts	The overall disparity in urban and rural women college students' access to education	Survey of student enrolment	The gap is relatively wide as compared to even disparity among private universities and colleges in China	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
8	Seeberg	2011	Outsider	Southeastern Shanxi	36 Guanlan Sisters and 27 of their families	Educational opportunities for girls living under severely constrained gendered socioeconomic and cultural circumstances using the empowerment dimensions: well-being, agency freedom, and achievement of capabilities	Interviews	Turning against their families' wishes has led to them being able to see the developed part of China, schooling results in self-confidence accompanied by psychological and cognitive control	Qualitative

9	Maslak	2011	Outsider	Rural Gansu Province	17 years old female	Lives of local Muslim women from the Dongxiang ethnic group	In-depth interviews and indirect observations	Concerning the empowerment concept, formal and informal education is a form of gender gap; school as compared to home, modern life to traditional life	Qualitative
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TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
10	Zhao, Z.	2011	Outsider	The capital of the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, China's capital Beijing, and the provincial capital of Hubei Province	Three universities, 19 female Mongol students (undergrads and postgrads), 25 male Mongol students, 27 Han students, eight other ethnic minorities, 43 academic and administrative staff	Socialist equalisation for minority women in higher education concerning empowerment and socialist egalitarianism	Interviews	The gap in minority women is due to being surrounded and formed by majority males in a socialist regime	Qualitative
11	Ren W.	2012	Mixed	Yunnan, Guizhou and Zhejiang	212 individuals (18–39)	Son/gender preference about to decline compared to the high sex ratio	Interviews	Son preference is declining, sex-selective abortion to ensure male offspring, the one-child policy could be relaxed to reduce high sex ratio	Qualitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
12	Qu, S.	2012	Outside insider	Shandong	108 farmers	Gender differences in factors for the performance of Bt cotton adoption by farmers	Interviews, Survey	Satisfaction level of Bt cotton performance, similarities with factors found in Iowa, USA government promotion, minor differences in terms of number of adopters of Bt cotton in favour of men	Mixed
13	Ren, W.	2012	Outside insider	Guangxi, Guizhou, Heilongjiang, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Liaoning, Shandong	Analysis framework; Census data 1993 onwards	The payoff to schooling in rural China; return to education in terms of overeducation, required education and undereducation in urban China; determinants of fertility in rural China	Reviewed studies, census data	The payoff is much higher for females, wage penalty for under-qualified workers more significant for females, over-educated women are advantageous; females have a higher return than males and reasons include not only the one-child policy (1979) but socioeconomic ones (e.g., education, marriage age and women occupations)	Mixed
14	Rhoads, R. et al.	2012	Mixed	Northern research university	15 women, 12 men	Challenges met by women academics	Semi-structured interviews	Four barriers hinder gender quality: double time work, glass ceiling, boys' club, and social exclusion, and comrades in arms	Qualitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
15	Hu, W.	2012	Insider	Dalian	47 high school students, one teacher	Teacher treatment impacted by gender	Ethnographic classroom observation	Existence of differential teacher treatment by gender	Qualitative
16	Liu, Q.	2012	Outside insider	Nationwide	Census data	Employment and labour market in urban China	Census data	Age, education, communist party membership, and marital status are entirely related to participation in the labour force and employment opportunities with minor effects on these observable differences between females and males	Quantitative
17	Gan, Z. et al.	2012	Mixed	Nationwide	1970 Han Chinese women (30–60 years)	Major depressive disorder concerning clinical features	Patient profiles	Education minimises chances of MDD; lower educational attainment is associated with more biological symptoms of MDD, not consistent with findings from European and US reports	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
18	Zhang, Q. et al.	2012	Mixed	Nationwide	3087 people, 50 counties	Family characteristics impacting men and women differently in self-employment participation in urban China	Survey	Lower rates for women due to family constraints and male preference	Quantitative
19	Sheng, X.	2012	Outside insider	Beijing	47 secondary school students and 50 parents	Cultural capital role in social differences impacting parental involvement in children's schooling and higher education choices	Semi-structured interviews	Cultural capital is gendered, mothers having a servicing role and fathers a controlling role, possibly influenced by Confucian tradition	Qualitative
20	Xiu, L. et al.	2013	Mixed	Nationwide	Census data (LHSCCC)	Providing evidence on male-female pay differences	Census data	Women receive lower than men (a quarter difference) affected by factors like education, communist party membership, supervisory roles, higher penalty rates for women due to ethnic reasons supported with educational differences or social elements such as marriage, discrimination	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
21	Changying, H. U.	2013	Insider	Nationwide	Census data and prior research	Role of education, mainly higher education, in empowering women	Census data and prior research	Women are gaining empowerment through education, but some problems related to the gender gap still exist, including rural-urban differences, jobs, and higher education, women's education, women's social responsibilities, laws promoting girls' education, women's rights, promoting the importance of education for women	Mixed
22	Ma, Y. et al.	2013	Mixed	Nationwide	1600 questionnaire, 1209 returned (seven key universities, eight ordinary universities, one independent college)	Cheating forms and reasons	Survey	There are positive and negative influence factors as organisational deterrence for the former and individual performance, peers cheating, individual pressure, and extracurricular activities for the latter	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
23	Li, Y. et al.	2013	Mixed	Nationwide	4 schools with 658 students aged 10–14	Digital inequality and its impact on social development and education	Survey	The gaps exist between urban and rural areas where both females and males have less digital access in rural areas. Further, females who do not join schools and stay home have even less digital access and awareness.	Quantitative
24	Yang, Y. et al.	2013	Mixed	Shanxi rural public schools; Qinghai minority public schools; and Beijing migrant schools	24 schools with 2514 grade 3 students (902 treatment classes and 1255 control classes; 72 schools, 5942 grades 3 and 5; 57 ethnic minority elementary schools with 1717 third and fourth-grade students)	Gender differences related to computers and education	Experiments: One Laptop Per Child (OLPC) programme, Computer Assisted Learning (CAL)	Use of Computers seem to have an equal effect on both females and males. It contributes to better education for both females and males.	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
25	Zeng, J. et al.	2014	Mixed	Nationwide	Empirical literature	Gender inequality in educational attainment	Meta-regression analysis across time, space, grade levels, and ethnicities	Gender inequality still exists yet is decreasing based on area (rural-urban) grade level, no gap in urban areas, or the nine-year compulsory education period	Quantitative
26	Qian, Y. et al.	2014	Outside insider	Nationwide	CGSS data	Highly educated women in urban areas as 'leftover ladies'	Census data, extended linear models	Men: more educated, more chances of marriage; women: more educated, fewer chances of marriage, mainly over 30; these due to the rapid growth of women's education and persistent traditional gender roles	Quantitative
27	Zhang, J. et al.	2014	Mixed	Liaoning, Human, Shandong	392 suicides (14–35), 16 counties of three provinces within community of 416	Male to female suicide ratio with a relatively high rate for women; reasons	Case-control psychological autopsy	Urban young Chinese believe in Confucianism and being married, protecting them from suicides, which are not valid for rural young Chinese; in rural areas, it is the more social and cultural base	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
28	Gammons	2014	Outsider	Urban China	11 females, aged 19–27	Gender, education and one-child policy impact on urban Chinese women	In-depth interviews	Concluding that whatever narrated experience should be taken into consideration and valued by society as they powerfully present the suffering of such women	Qualitative
29	Zhao, J et al.	2014	Insider	Jinan, Shandong	524 junior high school students	Effect of mothers' academic involvement in children's achievement and if children's gender is associated with such variables, all concerning the mediation of children's theory of intelligence	Survey	Academic involvement of mothers affects children's supportive involvement while controlling does not; autonomous support was related to girls only and controlling related to both	Quantitative
30	Xie, S et al.	2014	Insider	Liaoning, Heilongjiang, Jiangsu, Shandong, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Guangxi, and Guizhou	CHNS data 1989–2009	Impact of education in health	Census data	Education has no impact on both females and males' health behaviour except for the reduction of overweight for females	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
31	Li, H. et al.	2014	Mixed	Nationwide	Census data on human capital, purchasing power parity via a living cost index for 22 provinces	The human capital of provinces of China compared in terms of gender, urban and rural areas in terms of purchasing power parity via living cost index	Census data	Male to female differences are recorded in terms of total human capital between 1985–2010 (6.6) for men and only (6.1) for women	Quantitative
32	Lei, X. et al.	2014	Mixed	Nationwide	China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study (CHARLS, June 2011 and March 2012 on 17,708 respondents). CHARLS respondents will be followed every two years using a face-to-face, computer-aided personal interview (CAPI), the middle-aged and elderly population (45+)	Gender differences in cognition	Census data	Economic development and environmental improvement increase cognition ability, with women benefitting more	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
33	Gong, X et al.	2014	Mixed	Twenty-seven poor counties of Southwestern China (Guangxi, Sichuan, Guizhou, and Yunnan).	Southwest Basic Education project data	Estimation of gender gaps among primary and lower secondary school students in Chinese and maths	Census data	Minor gaps in Chinese in favour of girls especially in higher grades, minority increases gender gap too, the negative gender gap in maths, further investment is needed in female maths education	Quantitative
34	Fan, M. et al.	2015	Insider	three districts of Hangzhou	1362: 624 men and 738 women, ages 23–59	Association of body mass index with physical activity and sedentary behaviour, and if impacted by socio-demographic characteristics	The International Physical Activity Questionnaire	Significant differences were identified: women or people over 50 have a higher level of physical activity with increasing body mass index	Quantitative
35	Wang, L.	2015	Outside insider	Northern China, five public universities, one public college	66 rural female students: 51 undergrads and 15 grads)	Exploring rural Chinese females' conceptualisation of rural-urban divide and its impact on shaping their lives	Open-ended and in-depth interviews	Profound inequalities throughout their lives like the exclusion of rural students, feeling segregated when enrolled in urban campuses, and finding it challenging to integrate with urban people who feel superior to rural people	Qualitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
36	Zhang, H. et al.	2015	Mixed	Eight provinces that vary substantially in geography and socioeconomic level: Guangdong, Hubei, Jilin, Shaanxi, Shandong, Shanghai, Yunnan, and Zhejiang	SAGE data	The gender gap in self-perceived health concerning traditions of China such as son preference	Census data	Higher rates of arthritis, angina and eye diseases are the most significant contributor to the gender gap in health, among the most impacting reasons for discrimination in education (20 th century)	Quantitative
37	Shan, H. et al.	2015	Mixed	Rural women, Liushou women	Prior research and policy analysis related to vocational training for Liushou women	Women's equity in a vocational training status for Liushou women	Document analysis using women's empowerment framework and the social relations approach	Early to decide on the level of equity through the recently issued policies for vocational training for rural women and Liushou women, no significant involvement in projects based on social relations, and no involvement in policies and training	Qualitative
38	Yu, M.	2015b	Outside insider	Six districts of Beijing	15 migrant parents and teachers, nine social activists, government officials	Experiences of migrants	Interviews	A better understanding of their situation considering social, cultural, and economic factors is required in addition to reported gender discrimination ideologies and hierarchies	Qualitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
39	Wang, L.	2016	Insider	Zhonghua University, Huaxia University, Zhonghua Normal University, Huaxia University of China (Beijing), Huabei Provincial University, Huabei Municipal College (all urban areas locations)	66 rural female students	Rural women and their experiences on the discourse of quality in higher education	Interviews	Systematic marginalisation and discrimination by such a policy where they overcome it by developing alternative skills and building different knowledge	Qualitative
40	Askel-W. et al.	2016	Mixed	Beijing	2756 students between 10–15 years old attending 16 schools in Beijing	Social and emotional wellbeing of primary and middle schools' students	Questionnaires	General reported positive wellbeing scores even higher when compared to Australians; no gender differences were reported	Quantitative
41	Golley, J. et al.	2016	Mixed	Nationwide	China Family Panel Studies survey: 2010 and 2012	Educational inequality trends mainly inequality of opportunity	Census data	Determined by the divisive hukou, father's education, birth cohort, province, parents' communist party membership, gender, and family size and ethnicity	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
42	Campos, B. et al.	2016	Mixed	Nine provinces (Heilongjiang, Liaoning, Jiangsu, Shandong, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Guangxi, Guizhou), three municipalities (Beijing, Shanghai, Chongqing)	Chain Health and Nutrition Survey (CHNS) data 1993–2011	Education and income inequality between ethnic minorities and Han	Census data	Significant income inequality against minorities, including male to female gap, increase in return mainly for women minorities by further education were measured and identified too	Quantitative
43	Zhang, J. et al.	2016	Insider	Central University of Finance and Economics in Beijing	97 students with 49 in national economic administration and 48 in economics major, undergrads	Examine the view that females outperform males in a social science subject and particularly economic education	Three exams (course taught by the researcher)	Females performed better not due to ability, family background, etc. but due to more effort	Quantitative
44	Shen, K. et al.	2016	Mixed	Nationwide	China Family Panel Studies data, 2010 wave	Examining gender inequality based on public transfers in education, health care, and pension benefits	Census data	Public health care and pension transfers are biased toward men; public education transfers are even	Quantitative

(Continues)

TABLE A1 (Continued)

No.	Source	Date	Researcher identity	Setting	Sample	Phenomenon of interest	Design	Evaluation	Research type
45	Xu, Y. et al.	2017	Outside insider	Beijing, Tianjin, and Taiyuan Cities, economically among the most well developed in China	16 early childhood teachers	The gender impact of men's employment on ECTs	Online interviews and questionnaires	Collected perspectives indicated similar ones to those relating to gender stereotypes in China with an attempt for a minor deviation to enhance female gender inequality in all other aspects	Mixed
46	Shimbo	2017	Outsider	mountainous areas of southern Ningxia	Hui Muslim women who graduated from modern schools, compared to graduates of Arabic schools: 30 primary and secondary schools, 253 female teachers of which 229 married	Modernisation and globalisation effect on Hui Muslim women's lifestyle careers, and life course	Interviews and questionnaire	Graduates from Arabic school still keep their views and think that they can have jobs and family life which they are satisfied with as compared to those studying in modern schools to start to look at life differently and even view their religion differently; <i>education impact</i>	Qualitative
47	Alduais, A. et al.	2020	Mixed	Nationwide	Female education students and personnel: virtual data	Female education development and equity	Census bureau data for seven years	Crediting the presence of covert gender inequality as opposed to overt gender equality; discrediting the existence of procedural and substantive gender inequality	Quantitative

Note: These 47 sources are fully cited on the references list and are marked with an asterisk (*) to be distinguished from other cited sources.

APPENDIX 2

TABLE A2 PRISMA checklist

Section/topic	No.	Checklist item	Reported on page
TITLE:			1
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review, meta-analysis, or both.	1
ABSTRACT			1
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: background; objectives; data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal and synthesis methods; results; limitations; conclusions and implications of key findings; systematic review registration number.	1
INTRODUCTION			1–9
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known.	8–9
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	9
METHODS			10–14
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate if a review protocol exists, if and where it can be accessed (e.g., web address), and, if available, provide registration information including registration number.	11
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale. <i>SPIDER replaced this.</i>	11–12
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last searched.	12
Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	12
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	12
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	12–13
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	13

(Continues)

TABLE A2 (Continued)

Section/topic	No.	Checklist item	Reported on page
Risk of bias in individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level) and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	13
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means).	13
Synthesis of results	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies, if done, including measures of consistency (e.g., I^2) for each meta-analysis.	13
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	13–14
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression), if done, indicating which were pre-specified.	NA
RESULTS	14–19		
Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	14
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	14–16
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment (see item 12).	16–17
Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: (a) simple summary data for each intervention group, (b) effect estimates and confidence intervals, ideally with a forest plot.	17–18
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence intervals and measures of consistency.	18–19
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies (see Item 15).	19
Additional analysis	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression [see Item 16]).	NA
DISCUSSION	19–27		
Summary of evidence	24	Summarise the main findings including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance to key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policymakers).	19–26

(Continues)

TABLE A2 (Continued)

Section/topic	No.	Checklist item	Reported on page
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review-level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias).	26
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	26–27
FUNDING	27		
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review.	27

SPIDER replaced* PICOS.

From Moher et al. (2009). For more information, visit: www.prisma-statement.org.